

Search results for: Bagasse
 Date: Wed Mar 20 14:59:38 2024 (GMT+07:00)
 Search algorithm: Correlation
 Regions searched: 3495.26-649.90

Search results list of matches

Index	Match	Compound Name	Library Name
1	73	80.80 Chipboard w/ 3.6% methylene bis(phenylisocyanate)	HR Hummel Polymer and Additives
2	75	79.92 Chipboard w/ urea-formaldehyde condensate	HR Hummel Polymer and Additives
3	81	79.61 Chipboard K540 2.9% N	HR Hummel Polymer and Additives
4	40	79.38 CELLOPHANE	Hummel Polymer Sample Library
5	103	79.26 Cellulose + lignin	HR Hummel Polymer and Additives
6	68	79.11 Wood + melamine-formaldehyde resin	HR Hummel Polymer and Additives
7	80	78.57 Chipboard K540 4.2% N	HR Hummel Polymer and Additives
8	74	77.17 Chipboard w/ 6.5% methylene bis(phenylisocyanate)	HR Hummel Polymer and Additives
9	82	75.81 Chipboard P40 10.7% N	HR Hummel Polymer and Additives
10	733	73.77 CELLULOSE	HR Comprehensive Forensic FT-IR Collection